
THE MAIN PROBLEM OF LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract.

Although English is the third widely spoken languages in the world, many people continue to encounter numerous difficulties when attempting to master it. Moreover, these can be mistakes made not only by the pupil, but also by the instructors, teachers or the curriculum. Probably English language contains a lot of grammar structure nevertheless this particular issue is not the main problem for learners who come across with such questions. In this article it might be discovered some problematic circumstances of students who studied English language as a foreign language.

Key words.

Memorization, short-term memory, listening comprehension, phonemic perception, communicative teaching methods

Introduction

Learning a foreign language is quite laborious, costly and always demands learners to be attentive and spend endless amount of time to acquire it. Therefore, each pupil desires training outcomes that justify expectations and investments. To accomplish this, they should consider in advance what challenges may arise and how they will be addressed with the chosen instruction method. The majority of discussions between teachers from various institutions concern the same student difficulties. And instructors do not always know how to resolve these issues for a specific student.

Method

The first issue is forgetting foreign terms. This is always the case when attempting to memorize foreign words through rote memorization - cramming or other mnemonic techniques, outside of context and application practice.¹²⁸ By the way, word memorization using flash cards or, in a more modern form, a smartphone application, also refers to the mechanical method of memorization, and

¹²⁸ Tulyaganova Nargiza Farxod qizi, & Yusupova Shoira Batirovna. (2022). National Cultural Specificity of Speech Behavior in English and Uzbek. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 4, 80–82.

forgetting is inevitable. As a result of memorization devoid of semantic associations, foreign words are stored in short-term memory, where they rapidly evaporate. According to our methodology, words are presented promptly in the context of their use, and most frequently not separately, but in phrases, sentences, and dialogues, i.e. in a semantic composite. This corresponds to the natural method of mastering a foreign language, in which words in our memory and consciousness form a kind of family known as semantic fields. This, along with repeated repetition and frequent use in various contexts, is the only reason why words are stored in long-term memory. So that you will remember it even years after studying it.¹²⁹

Misunderstanding of a foreign language is the next problem. Listening misunderstanding is related to more than just a deficiency in language practice. The pupil appears to be learning English; he can read texts and even construct simple sentences, but he cannot comprehend the speech of others at all.¹³⁰ This is a common issue that even seasoned pupils encounter. Again, the issue is a paucity of practice. If a person's Listening skill is underdeveloped, he should hearken to as much English speech as feasible. One of the most essential components, listening comprehension, is neglected by the majority of teaching strategies. In contrast to music, phonemic hearing allows us to perceive and comprehend speech. This is the basis provided by the constitution and physiology of the brain, upon which the future of language will be constructed. Without a foundation, there is no language. Developing phonemic perception in a foreign language is essential! Consequently, nearly half of classes with us will be devoted to this discipline.¹³¹

Confusing about tenses is the third issue that could be encountered each of students. In general it is the wide spread problem among language learners, due to the fact that English language include 12 tenses and their passive voice forms. Obviously every student after hearing the quantity of tenses and their differences among them might be the reason for lack of motivation to learning certain foreign language. Grammar stands as a basic and foundational aspect of language without it speaker cannot deliver his or her information intelligibly and to avoid such a

¹²⁹ Razzakberdiyeva, U. D. (2022). PHRASAL VERBS IN MODERN ENGLISH: TERMINOLOGY, FEATURES, CLASSIFICATION. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 *Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(06), 51-54.*

¹³⁰ Jumaeva, N. K. (2022). LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HYPONOMIC RELATIONS AND DEEPLY ANALYZING ITS FEATURES IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. *Academic Research in Educational Sciences*, 3(4), 535-542.

¹³¹ Узакбоева, Р. (2022). Comparative characteristics of archaisms and historicisms. *Переводоведение: проблемы, решения и перспективы*, (1), 481-482.

circumstance it should be learned on a real life situation. When grammar is based on the actual use of a foreign language, it becomes a valuable ally and friend. Otherwise, we end up with expressions that a native speaker would never use or even comprehend. From practice to theory, therefore, communicative teaching methods also follow this path and may achieve specific objectives.¹³²

Result

Learning foreign language, as it is mentioned before, is a laborious work and may reduce the motivation of studying it because of its otherness to learners native language. Thus students may comprehend that they cannot utilize it correctly or under pressure they might confuse about the grammar structure which leads misunderstanding and losing interest of studying foreign language.¹³³ The primary motivator in language acquisition is motivation. It is motivation that encourages student to begin studying English and pursue his objective. No teacher will compel a student to learn English if he lacks motivation and does not understand why he must do so. Therefore, students must determine early on why they are studying English with an eye to be motivated by this objective.

It could be:

A large salary

An interesting job

Studying abroad and travelling around the world

The most essential factor is student's sincere desire and he must understand for himself in the matter of motivation: learner need to act.

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¹³² Akmalxonov, S. F. A. (2022). THE HISTORY OF USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN DIDACTIC WAY. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(12), 197-201.

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